

Comparative analysis on virtual private network in the internet of things gateways

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ABSTRACT

A virtual private network (VPN) connects a private network to the internet, primarily the public network, through a secure tunnel. Using a local area network (LAN) segment, users can send and receive data from their colleagues in different locations on the network. The development of VPN allows users to gain access to company applications and databases. Therefore, data can be transmitted through a secure tunnel without the need to configure port forwarding for the internet of things (IoT) gateway, allowing users to access it from any location in the world. A method such as dataplicity and pitunnel was examined to compare with the conventional setting. This research paper examines the current deployment of VPN connections in IoT gateways, discussing their characteristics, benefits, and drawbacks, as well as comparing them. The advantage of this method is that the IoT gateway is always accessible and has internet connectivity, which is a significant benefit. Dataplicity is a more trustworthy option because they offer excellent assistance for both the backend and frontend environments.

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1. INTRODUCTION

People nowadays are keen to get them up-to-date, with the accessibility of making maximum use of the internet. They want the information right on the palm. This goes the same for their house, as they can remotely monitor and control home appliances using a web-based graphical user interface (GUI) [1] or smartphones [2]. Whether in the office or at the sandy beaches, they can easily access their home regardless of time and place. Users can check the temperature [3], humidity [4], rainy seasons [5], gas leakage [6], and even watering their plants [7]. All they need is a smart gateway connected to the internet and communication within the sensors and actuators [8]–[12]. Users can monitor the sensors and control the actuators from the web-based GUI. For example, the air-conditioner operates within 30-minutes resident reaches home, the microwave heats the food, and the water sprinkler activates when it is time to water the plants or sense the soil is drying up [13], [14]. Eventually, this is the so-called self-healing IoT gateway [15]–[18]. Saito *et al.* [19] defined a home gateway as the ingress point between a personal area network and a public access network. This gateway can allow users to monitor, control, and analyze on a day-to-day basis. The device is connected to the sensors or actuators, connected directly via serial communication or zigbee [20] or long-range radio (LoRa) wirelessly [21]. Data collected from the sensors is then passed to the gateway before

being sent to cloud storage [22]–[24]. When the data is gathered, the gateway can analyze the provided data, such as gas leakage or surrounding temperature is too high, and take appropriate action, such as alarming users about the gas leakage via short message service (SMS) or email and activating the air ventilation [25]. This self-healing ability can save human life and help users safeguard the house.

A secured connection is compulsory to avoid breaches from the inappropriate gestures to the home network [26]. As many people live around us, predators try to sniff important data in the network [27]. Thus, having a virtual private network (VPN) connection is compulsory for IoT gateway to operate [28]. VPN enables the secure extension of a private network over an untrusted public network [29]. The internet engineering task force (IETF) has defined several protocols for establishing a VPN [30]. Secure sockets layer (SSL) and transport layer security (TLS) are two of them [31]. TLS is a protocol that combines the SSL certificates of its predecessor into a single standard. SSL/TLS has been extensively developed to address security and trust concerns while remaining transparent to the user. As a result, users create wireless VPNs using this protocol. The SSL/TLS protocols define the mechanisms to ensure secure data transmission over the internet [32]. The IETF controls the standards. The protocols are cryptographic protocols that ensure the security of computer network communications. Numerous protocols in various flavours are widely used in web browsing, email, instant messaging, and voice over internet protocol (VoIP) applications. For example, TLS, usually coupled with hypertext transfer protocol (HTTP), secures the web and uses the hypertext transfer protocol secure (HTTPS) uniform resource identifier (URI) scheme [33], [34]. TLS is the internet's cryptographic protocol. It comprises protocols for negotiating cryptographic parameters, encrypting and decrypting data, and reporting errors encountered during the process. As a result, a security analysis of any cryptographic protocol is required to identify any vulnerabilities and to assess the protocol's security properties [35].

Although the pandemic hit us in early 2020, the technology did not stop us from venturing into more and more newly developed methods and approaches. Everyone stayed back at home, but at the same time, we needed to gather valuable information from our site. Our site might be on an urban or rural site, and it might be that our site got no copper or fiber connection but eventually had a mobile data connection (4G or 5G) on our site. The latest 5G network for IoT devices [36] provides a large broadcast capacity that supports up to 65,000 connections at a time. based on the telecom regulatory authority of india (TRAI), 93% of broadband penetration is in the urban area, while 29.3% is broadband penetration in India's rural areas [37]. Ahmed *et al.* discuss implementing IoT devices in rural areas with a Wi-Fi based Long Distance and 6LoWPAN enabled WSN network [38]. Kautsarina and Kusumawati [39] discuss the supportive technologies for IoT devices in rural areas. Carrillo and Seki [40] compare the long-term evolution (LTE) and the LoRAWAN application in rural areas involving UAVs to quantify the gain ratio coverage compared to the terrestrial scenario. Mohammed Sadeeq *et al.* [41] discuss security, storage and computational performance, and other challenges regarding cloud-IoT. Pourqasem [42] proposed the Cloud-based IoT integration, and the infrastructure was based on storing, processing and communication features. Providing the cloud-based IoT influences data format and connecting devices, thus providing the web service-based communication between IoT devices and the cloud [43].

In this paper best method connecting IoT devices with the cloud is proposed without having a copper/fiber connection and solely depending on the 4G/5G connection. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first work that focuses on integrating a secure protocol at the embedded interface, which is unique. Raspberry Pi is used as an example of an IoT gateway in our pilot deployment of the model for IoT gateway to demonstrate how this could be accomplished. As a result of a large number of low-cost and resource-constrained lightweight Internet of Things devices that are being connected over the internet, security measures have historically not been compatible with the processing power of these embedded controllers. because raspberry Pi can be integrated with Wi-Fi, serial peripheral interface (SPI), narrow-band imaging (NBI), Zigbee, LoRA, and a variety of other protocol connectivity, it is an excellent choice for our IoT gateway model. Raspbian, which is a Debian-based operating system, is also available for the Raspberry Pi. It can be configured to run a LAMP (Linux Apache, MySQL, and PHP), allowing the Raspberry Pi to function as a web server. A method such as Dataplicity and PiTunnel was analyzed to compare with the conventional setting. By using this method, users can connect to their device via internet connections from a remote location, where it makes the device's private address accessible from the internet via "IP tunnelling" technology, making the device reachable from anywhere in the world.

2. METHOD

The Raspberry Pi 3 model B is the hardware used in this study. The Raspberry Pi 3 model B is the most recent model available. The Raspberry Pi runs Linux and Windows operating systems (OS), allowing this credit-card-sized computer to act as an IoT gateway [44]. It also supports wired communication protocols like SPI and inter-integrated circuit (I2C), as well as wireless protocols like Zigbee and LoRa. In addition,

this minicomputer, powered by a 1.4 GHz Broadcom chip, can function as a standard computer with a camera port, 40 pin GPIO, and Wi-Fi connections.

IoT gateway should provide and support internal and external data exchange in a smart home scenario [45]. Moreover, it is reliable to communicate with wired and wireless sensor nodes. Therefore, the IoT gateway need these requirements to work [46]:

- Data forwarding: the IoT gateway's primary function is to send data from sensor nodes or the internet to receiving applications or software bound to its addresses.
- Protocol conversion: the IoT gateway should convert communication protocols between the 802.15.4/Zigbee/LoRa wireless protocol and TCP/IP protocols. The IoT gateway should collect packets from sensor nodes using short-distance wireless communication protocols (such as Zigbee) and long-distance wireless communication protocols (such as LoRa), then send them to telecommunication networks or the internet using 3G, Wi-Fi, and other network interfaces. As a result, the IoT gateway should analyze and repackage it before capsulating and sending it using telecommunication protocols after receiving sensor data.
- Management and control: the IoT gateway should manage and control the sensor nodes in addition to receiving and uploading data. When the gateway receives commands from a remote server, it should process them and then send them to the sensor nodes via IoT gateway to manage and control the sensor network.

Dataplicity [47] and PiTunnel [48] are two VPN providers for IoT gateway that were investigated. Remote access to the IoT gateway is available from both providers. The IoT gateway will be installed with installers from both providers. Dataplicity is nothing more than a VPN for your Raspberry Pi, as shown in Figure 1. This feature not only allows users to access their Raspberry Pi from anywhere, but it also enables them to "wormhole" a web server through the system, allowing them to run their own little website from the convenience of their all-in-one computer.

Figure 1. Dataplicity system flowchart [47]

However, PiTunnel differs from dataplicity in that it makes some of its own modifications. Users can connect to their little computer via a terminal or the web by simply running a few commands on the local Pi. A one-of-a-kind feature is the ability to launch a command prompt from within the browser. Other services are heavily reliant on remote terminals for their operations. Although PiTunnel includes that feature, it is primarily concerned with tunnelling, which means that users can access any network service that is running on their raspberry Pi from anywhere in the world, whether it is using the HTTP protocol or some other custom protocol, without having to worry about setting up complicated network routing or static IP addresses as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. PiTunnel system flowchart [48]

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

To choose the best VPN connections to be implemented into the IoT gateway, a few sets of tests were applied to the VPN to choose the best one. These tests focus on the applications between the VPN provider and IoT gateway. The main goal is to see the VPN provider control, access and modify the IoT gateway either thru web-based or GUI.

For these, three different tests were made to see the following values: i) remote access from VPN website, ii) proper uniform resource locator (URL) designation, and iii) diagnostics tools for the IoT gateway. For the test to be done, both VPN provider installers need to install into IoT gateway. The installer command looks the same between the providers. They use the curl command to fetch and install the software into the IoT gateway. It takes time for the installer to be downloaded and installed into the IoT gateway.

3.1. Remote access

We need to know if dataplicity and PiTunnel allow users to remote access the IoT gateway for the first test. Remote access is the ability to access a computer from a remote location. The ability of remote access is provided either thru LAN, wide area network (WAN) or VPN. In addition, both providers allow users to remote the IoT gateway from the internet through their website. As we can see here in Figure 3, Dataplicity allows users to remotely access the user's device thru the Dataplicity agent that was previously installed. Dataplicity Wormhole allows connections from the internet, going to the IoT gateway terminal. The connections are then passed to the Dataplicity IoT router, and the user can see the terminal. For a website hosted in the IoT gateway, Dataplicity Wormhole open port 80 for access. The URL will change to device_id.dataplicity.io. The URL is accessible as long as there is an internet connection from the IoT gateway. IoT gateway must have Apache running so that the website hosted inside can be seen from the internet.

Figure 3. Dataplicity VPN connection model [49]

Both Dataplicity and PiTunnel provide SSL/TLS connections to the IoT Gateway. These encryptions protocols offer security on the data transactions from the internet to the IoT Gateway. The test confirms that the providers can give full access to the user to remote to the IoT, as referred to in Figure 4 and Figure 5.

Figure 4. Dataplicity remote access

Figure 5. PiTunnel remote access

3.2. Proper URL designation

The user needs to install the webserver into the IoT gateway for the second test. The user can install either Nginx or Apache on the IoT gateway. Dataplicity provides two types of URLs to the user, where Dataplicity called the application a Wormhole. They use HTTPS embed in the domain to deliver security. One is a free domain, where the user uses a free given domain provided by Dataplicity, while the other one is paid domain, where the user needs to pay the domain monthly recurrence, and the user is free to choose its domain. Dataplicity offers a subdomain, which is the URL is: <subdomain>.dataplicity.io.

For IoT gateway, we installed Joomla into the webserver. Joomla is a content management system (CMS) that is very popular for designing a website. It has a user-friendly front end and back end design. It uses the what you see is what you get (WYSIWYG) concept. According to Zhu *et al.* [50], the visible part of a web page includes tools like the Web Browser, the displayed contents, and the layout, while the invisible part includes the code written on the web page, such as extensible hypertext markup language (XHTML), cascading style sheets (CSS), and so on. The Joomla website template is crisp and manageable, allowing the user to amend at the back end. The structure and layout are user-controllable and require no website coding

savvy; thus, it is constructive. As we can see here in Figure 6, the layout is very structured and in place. However, the title and the menus are incorrect positions. The article also is in its location. This is what the user needs for the IoT gateway.

Referring to Figure 7, PiTunnel, on the other hand, provides a free subdomain, and the user cannot choose its domain. PiTunnel also provides an HTTPS connection to the IoT gateway port. When the user accesses the Joomla template's website, the structure is miserable and improper. The menu is moving far below, and the article is shifted.

Figure 6. Dataplicity joomla layout

Figure 7. PiTunnel joomla layout

3.3. Diagnostic tools

For the third test, diagnostics tools for the IoT gateway. The diagnostics tools are vital as part of the IoT gateway, and the user needs to know the basic and in-depth condition of IoT gateway hardware. Dataplicity provides diagnostics tools, allowing the user to monitor system configuration from the user's mobile phone. Dataplicity segmented the tools into three parts: networking, system and advanced.

The networking button tells the user which interfaces are connected to the internet, as seen in Figure 8. It also stated the network traffic data, giving a real-time chart of the network traffic transmitted to or from the IoT gateway. This gives the user the first impression if there are suspicious attacks from outside. The high incoming traffic pattern from the internet will show the user that a flood ping or distributed denial of service (DDoS) attack is possible. After information theft, DDoS attacks are the second most common cybercrime. Flood attacks using the DDoS transmission control protocol (TCP) can quickly deplete the cloud's resources, consume most of its bandwidth, and damage an entire cloud project [51]. The user can recognize and take appropriate actions, such as appending the IP address or moving the IP address to a blacklist. The system

button tells the user the central processing unit (CPU), random-access memory (RAM), and disk usage conditions. The advanced button provides the ifconfig status, domain name system (DNS) resolver, mount point, and cpuinfo. Meanwhile, in Figure 9 PiTunnel only provided IoT gateway OS version, memory usage, CPU usage and temperature, graphics processing unit (GPU) temperature and active tunnel.

Figure 8. Dataplicity network traffic data

Figure 9. PiTunnel IoT gateway status

Table 1. Comparison between conventional setting, Dataplicity and PiTunnel

Description	Conventional setting	Dataplicity	PiTunnel
Network knowledge	Intermediate/advanced	Beginner	Beginner
Port setting	Both on router and IoT device, vulnerable to DDoS attack	No changes to be done	No changes to be done
IoT gateway behaviour	Cannot detect	Can be monitor	Can be monitor
Security	WPA2 encryption	Client-initiated HTTPS	HTTPS Security

4. CONCLUSION

IoT gateway provides users with a web-based GUI for monitoring and controlling purposes, and users can do remote access to the IoT gateway in case of system support. The need for a virtual private network in the IoT gateway networking delivers security and private management. The non-authentic user will be prohibited from accessing the IoT gateway and reducing the possibility of hacking into the IoT gateway. In this paper, the authors analyzed VPN providers into IoT gateway for smart homes to choose the best for a set of scenarios using remote access, proper website URL and diagnostics tool. Concluding the VPN connectivity, Dataplicity provides such a reasonable provision for the user. Moreover, Dataplicity is a more reliable choice as they provide tremendous support for the backend and frontend environments. This connection can be expanded into smart agriculture, smart farming, smart factory, smart water sensor and

eHealth. Future research will also include a look at large-scale IoT infrastructure, penetration testing, and a live demonstration of a malicious attack.

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